

A Comprehensive Review of Fruit Adulteration Detection Techniques and Applications.

Snehal S. Datwase¹, Dr. Charansing N. Kayte*², Dr. Ratnadeep R. Deshmukh³

1. Dept. of computer science and It, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University Chh. Sambhajinagar, India.
2. Department of Digital and Cyber Forensic, Chh. Sambhajinagar Maharashtra, India
3. Dept. of computer science and It, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University Chh. Sambhajinagar, India.

Abstract— To ensure the integrity of fruit goods, powerful detection approaches are required because fruit adulteration poses a severe danger to consumer health and culinary authenticity. This review paper offers a thorough analysis of several techniques used to identify adulterated fruit, including conventional and cutting-edge methods. Applications of these methods to other fruit kinds are discussed, with a focus on how well they identify adulterants like artificial coloring, preservatives, and ripening agents. The paper also explores the shortcomings and new problems associated with the current approaches, with the goal of assisting in the creation of more dependable techniques for fruit adulteration detection.

Keywords— Adulterants, Deep learning, Fruit adulteration, Machine learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

In addition to their delicious flavors, fruits are nutrient-dense superfoods with therapeutic benefits that greatly improve human health. Many fruits have long been used in traditional medicine to treat a wide range of illnesses. Secondary metabolites, which are naturally occurring substances with biological activity, are found in fruits and are essential for treating and preventing a wide range of illnesses. Fruits are primarily composed of organic acids, vitamins, sugars, pectin, water, carbs, and starch; proteins and lipids are present in smaller quantities.

A diet rich in diversity and rich in fruits helps prevent diseases like diabetes, heart disease, stroke, obesity, constipation, and hypertension as well as improve general health [1]. Adopting a fruit-rich diet will help you stay ahead of the game in terms of maintaining your health and averting certain ailments.

Since the last ten years have seen an increase in thorough research on natural medicines, plants have been important sources of natural compounds that have improved human health [2]. In addition to their traditional use in food preparation to enhance flavor and scent, spices have antibacterial qualities [3]. These spices offer a natural barrier against microorganisms in addition to enhancing the flavor of food preparations.

Some spices are used as natural antibacterial agents in food preparation in addition to their aromatic and flavor-enhancing properties. Certain natural compounds present in these spices give them antibacterial capabilities [4]. So, by utilizing the inherent antibacterial properties of these spice-derived compounds, adding these plant-derived components to our diets improves not just the taste experience but also our general health and wellbeing.

Any material that is added to food items with the goal of reducing their inherent quality and composition in order to increase their market value is considered adulteration. In technical terms, "fruit" refers to the fleshy or dry, maturing ovary that houses the seeds of blooming plants. Fruits such as apricots, bananas, grapes, corn, tomatoes, cucumbers and almonds (in their shell) are included in this. But in common parlance, "fruit" usually refers to delicious, matured ovaries that are either pulpy or succulent. Fruits are vital parts of a healthy diet since they are high in dietary fiber, vitamins, and antioxidants. Although fresh fruits can spoil quickly, their freshness can be preserved by refrigeration or by using oxygen-removal techniques when packaging or storing them. Furthermore, fruits can be dried up and turned into a variety of products like

juices, jams, and jellies, which offer palatable and practical substitutes for eating [5]. Fruits' nutritional advantages can be savoured for longer when they are preserved properly.

Some hazardous chemicals are frequently added to fruits in order to improve its appearance, texture, and yield. Common adulterants in fruit and vegetable waxes include oxytocin and saccharin, as well as colours originating from petroleum, including substances that are forbidden such as copper sulphate, calcium carbide, and metallic compounds. These compounds help brinjal, cucumber, gourd, and watermelon grow so that the fruits look better. They also accelerate the ripening process by making fruits like watermelon and muskmelon sweeter. In response to concerns regarding food adulteration, the Food Safety and Standards Administration of India (FSSAI) released a paper called DART, or "detect adulteration with rapid test." This paper provides customers with easy-to-follow steps for spotting possible food adulteration. Notably, store shelves are frequently stocked with artificially coloured soft beverages, confectionery, baking mixes, and breakfast cereals that have no natural counterpart. Avoiding artificially coloured products that are red, orange, yellow, green, or blue is advised for people who desire to avoid possibly dangerous food dyes in those products.

The drawback, nevertheless, is in the less evident products. Even though they can seem natural, certain foods have had their colours enhanced or changed by chemical processing and artificial colours. This may provide consumers a false impression and encourage them to trust these products in spite of any possible health dangers. For example, oranges are not always orange all year round, so some growers retain the aesthetic appeal of their produce by using FDA-approved chemical colours, even though these colorings may be harmful to human health. Choosing organic oranges, which don't include chemical colouring, or oranges grown in California or Arizona is advised to allay these worries [6].

II. LIST OF ADULTERANTS AND TESTING PROCEDURES

A. Oxytocin

Testing Method: To quantify oxytocin levels precisely and affordably, high-performance thin-layer chromatography is used. The linearity, accuracy, precision, and detection and quantification limitations of this approach have all been verified.

B. Saccharin

Impact on Health: A coal tar byproduct called saccharin has been related to allergies and cancer. **Testing Process:** Although saccharin itself may not be tested in fruits directly, consumers must be aware of its existence in the food sector.

C. Calcium Aluminum

Effects on Health: Calcium carbide is a recognized carcinogen that can result in cancer and liver failure in addition to gastrointestinal problems and jaundice. **Method of Testing:** A straightforward method is to combine the solution with water to wash the fruits. A change in colour signifies the application of calcium carbide for ripening.

D. Wax

Fruit waxing is the process of using a variety of techniques to apply a thin layer of edible wax to the outside surface. Fruit quality can be adversely affected by excessive waxing, which can result in problems like wax whitening or chalking, particularly when the fruit is exposed to heat or moisture [7].

E. Acid adulteration and colour

Method for Testing Colour: Soak raisins in water and HCL solution; adulteration is indicated by a discernible change in colour. Acid can be tested by sprinkling water on dried fruit and using litmus paper; the presence of acid is shown by a noticeable change in colour. A new document called DART (detect

adulteration with rapid test) from the Food Safety and Standards Administration of India (FSSAI) gives customers easy-to-follow instructions on how to spot adulterated food. Studies highlight the possible health hazards linked to artificial dyes, which are frequently included in food products with colour, and advise customers to choose organic substitutes instead. To prevent any health risks related to FDA-approved chemical dyes used to enhance orange colour, it is recommended to select organic oranges or those cultivated in certain regions.

III.LITERATURE REVIEW

The issue of global food adulteration, as investigated by researchers such as Tomar and Alka, presents a significant risk to public health in both wealthy and developing nations. Food becomes potentially hazardous when adulterants like melamine, calcium carbide, and artificial colouring are added. Profit-driven incentives result in the addition of poisonous ingredients, chalk powder, and metanil yellow, which can cause cancer, anaemia, and paralysis, among other health problems. The literature emphasises how easily spices can become contaminated during cultivation, which can lead to an increased risk of food-borne infections. Tomar and Alka underscore the pressing need for all-encompassing steps to prevent adulteration, highlighting its worldwide ramifications and the requirement for strict protocols to safeguard the food supply's integrity [8].

N. Ogrinc et.al this study of the literature explores the critical field of characterising and identifying potential adulteration in three essential Mediterranean products: wine, fruit juices, and olive oil. The study emphasises the importance of mass spectrometry (MS) and high-resolution nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, two potent methods, in product analysis. The focus is especially on the complementary use of isotope-ratio mass spectrometry (IRMS) and site-specific natural isotopic fractionation nuclear magnetic resonance (SNIF-NMR), supported by chemometric techniques. These methods provide a thorough method for spotting any adulteration and guaranteeing the integrity of vital Mediterranean goods. They are crucial instruments for deciphering the complexities of food products [9].

Rumila Sitaram Kumar et.al this review of the literature looks into the practice of adulterating fruits, which involves adding compounds on purpose to change their natural makeup in order to make more money. Fruits are a group of vegetables that are prized for their nutritional value because they are high in antioxidants, vitamins, and dietary fibre. Techniques for preservation such as cooling and oxygen extraction are essential. The review does draw attention to fruits' vulnerability to adulteration, which could compromise their nutritious value. The body of research supports strict regulations to protect the integrity and quality of these essential food ingredients [10].

In this paper Nan-Yu Cheng et.al this work focuses on using frequency-domain diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS) to noninvasively determine apples' optical characteristics. Employing two source-detector separations (SDS) of 1 and 5 mm, and laser diode wavelengths at 660 and 980 nm corresponding to chlorophyll and water absorption peaks, the research analyses the association between optical features and physiological changes in apples during a 14-day period. At 660 nm with a 1 mm SDS, the decrease in the absorption coefficient (μ_a) and the lowered scattering coefficient (μ_s') correspond with the breakdown of enzyme components of cell walls and chlorophyll. Comparably, after 14 days, the drop in μ_a at 980 nm with a 5 mm SDS shows a decrease in the amount of water in the apple's outer flesh, whereas the drop in μ_s' at the same wavelength, therefore the softening of apples during ripening is correlated with SDS [11].

Sneha S et.al this analysis highlights the need of guaranteeing high-quality food and addresses the widespread problem of food adulteration worldwide. It draws attention to the increasing interest in using deep learning and machine learning methods to identify adulterants in food products. The study gives a broad review of the state-of-the-art in food adulteration detection, taking into account both established analytical methods and the recently developed area of machine learning. It presents recent research papers

that describe the goals, procedures, and samples used for detecting adulteration in a variety of food items, summarising different approaches and applications. In addition, the assessment highlights the difficulties in detecting food adulteration and emphasises how adulteration techniques are evolving quickly, highlighting the necessity of creative and flexible solutions to guarantee food safety and quality [12].

S. P. S. Brighty et.al they discusses the vital issue of guaranteeing food safety and purity for human use. Recognising the importance of unadulterated and healthy food, the study introduces an Internet of Things (IoT) based food and formalin detection technique. This novel technology detects formalin in fruits and vegetables by using machine-learning techniques. The device uses a Raspberry Pi3 and a volatile chemical HCHO gas sensor to quantify the formalin concentration and correlate it with the food item's sampled output voltage. The fruits and vegetables are then categorised using a variety of machine learning methods in accordance with the attributes that were retrieved. Predicting formalin concentration at various temperatures is more accurate when supervised machine learning methods are incorporated. Interestingly, the system shows that it can discriminate between formalin that is naturally existing and that has been artificially added. Through the use of IoT and machine learning technology, this development effectively detects formalin in fruits and vegetables, marking a significant leap in food product quality and safety [13]. Bharathi Avula et.al thorough analysis emphasises the wide range of therapeutic benefits of anthocyanins and their potential to treat a variety of human conditions, such as cardiovascular disease, neurodegenerative illnesses, antioxidative stress, and cognitive decline. Water-soluble polyphenols containing sugar moieties called anthocyanins are widely distributed in berries and coloured fruits. Methodologies for the analysis, measurement, and chemical profiling of anthocyanins over the last twenty years are gathered. These include spectroscopic and chromatographic approaches, which can be used alone or in combination. The stability of anthocyanins is affected by a number of factors, including pH, light exposure, solvents, metal ions, enzymes, and proteins. The review discusses anthocyanin sources, such as fruits and berries, along with their botanical identities and yields. The topic of adulteration driven by economics as a result of increased customer demand is also covered. The final section of the paper briefly reviews the medical applications and health advantages of anthocyanins. Electronic databases from January 2000 to November 2022, such as PubMed, Science Direct, SciFinder, and Google Scholar, were searched for relevant literature [14]. J Fitelsox this work suggests a straightforward method for efficiently separating sorbitol and sugars in fruit juices using gas-liquid chromatography (GLC). All fruits include extra glucose peaks in addition to the major fructose peaks. Sorbitol is present in some fruits (such as cherry, plum, apple, and pear) but not in smaller berries. Bigger fruits have more sugar as well. Authentic fruits and commercial samples were used to validate the approach and confirm distinctive characteristics. Using aberrant sugar patterns, the process successfully detected adulteration in commercial concentrates. The method's dependability was established through collaborative studies, which led to the official recommendation that it be adopted as the initial step for evaluating the sugar and sorbitol content in fruit juices [15].

Wilbur W. Widmer et.al Juice adulteration provides a substantial economic challenge, moving from basic dilution to sophisticated procedures aimed at masking the manipulation. Major problems that regulatory agencies deal with include juice admixture, the inclusion of colourants, amino acids, and organic acids, as well as the undeclared addition of sugar and pulp wash. Another regulatory concern is figuring the juice's place of origin. Though many approaches have been developed to identify adulterated juice, only a handful of them work well against advanced methods. Methodologies such as isotopic studies, SNIF-NMR, HPLC, tracer addition, UV/VIS spectrophotometry, ICP-AES, electrochemical detection, and pattern recognition are all rigorously evaluated in this research [16].

Misgana Banti et.al Food integrity is seriously jeopardised by food fraud and adulteration, which involve the purposeful or inadvertent insertion of non-food components. Ethiopia is among the many foods worldwide impacted by this problem. Recent reports in Ethiopia showed injera adulteration with sawdust. Detection techniques are difficult, particularly when the adulterants' characteristics resemble those of the meal. Governments, organisations, and individuals must work together to address this. To protect

consumers and the food supply chain, researchers and academics are essential in evaluating, identifying foods that are sensitive, and developing detection techniques [17].

Sanjitha M et.al In order to identify fruit adulteration, this study uses image pattern classification, which combines colour and textural information. Images of both healthy and contaminated fruits must be gathered and pre-processed, shape, colour, and texture features must be extracted, and an image classification method called a support vector machine must be used. The study uses the DARKNET-53 model and the real-time object identification system YOLOv3. Important layers that are primarily utilised to classify images are skipped. The study combines the high accuracy VGG16 and YOLOv3 deep learning libraries, such as Keras and OpenCV. In the 2014 ILSVRC challenge, VGG16 finished in second place with a 92.7% accuracy rating. In conclusion, this research combines feature extraction, picture classification, and machine learning to improve fruit adulteration detection, hence enhancing food safety and quality assurance [18].

Calle JL et.al. In order to detect and quantify adulterants in fruit juices, this work combines FT-IR and machine learning, tackling the widespread problem of adulteration. We looked at three different pure fruit juices that had been tampered with using grape juice. Based on the results, unique clustering for juice types was found. Machine learning techniques, such as SVM, RF, and LDA, detected adulteration with an accuracy of above 97%. Support vector regression and partial least squares regression were quite successful for quantification. Consumers and the industry stand to gain significantly from this strategy if fruit juice authenticity and quality are maintained [19].

Momtaz M et.al Food adulteration refers to intentional modifications made to food quality for financial advantage, influencing qualities including colour, flavour, and shelf life. Substitution is frequently used to improve apparent quality by changing the nutritional value or adding substances. This can involve substituting different species, proteins, fats, or plant-based ingredients. Deceptive methods, such as falsely claiming the provenance of food, are used to increase market demand. For immediate effects, adulteration introduces organic and synthetic substances, resulting in health problems and financial losses. Diarrhoea, nausea, allergies, diabetes, and cardiovascular issues can all be brought on by contaminated food. Even some adulterants have cancer-causing qualities. In order to preserve the public's health, this review examines the many types of food adulteration and their effects on health [20].

Chetan Raju P H et.al Fruit purity and lack of adulteration are requirements for fruit quality, which is essential for human health. Some traders preserve fruit with the poisonous substance formalin to increase fruit durability and attractiveness. An effective system using Visual Geometry Group 16 (CNN) architecture is used to detect formalin, replacing manual inspection and improving accuracy. This method takes pictures of fruit, analyses them for size and colour, and then determines adulteration using image pixel information. It simplifies the inspection procedure, guarantees fruit quality, and is advantageous to the industry as well as customers [21].

Brighty SP et.al the method described in this work uses machine learning to detect the presence of formalin in food and is IoT-based. To detect the formalin content in fruits and vegetables, a volatile chemical HCHO gas sensor is attached to a Raspberry Pi 3. The classification of food is done using a variety of machine learning techniques, and supervised machine learning allows for precise formalin concentration prediction and distinction between naturally occurring and artificially added formalin. With the use of this technology, the food business and customers may both be assured of the quality and safety of their food [22].

Miaw CS et.al Detection of adulterants in grape nectars by attenuated total reflectance Fourier-transform mid-infrared spectroscopy and multivariate classification strategies Food authenticity is essential for consumer trust and safety. Deceptive practises, such as using less expensive fruits in fruit beverages, are a frequent problem. ATR-FTIR and multivariate classification are used in this work to identify adulteration in grape nectars, particularly the addition of apple or cashew juice. It uses one-class and multiclass methodologies with an analysis of 126 samples, using modelling techniques including SIMCA, PLS-DA, and PLS-DM. With virtually 100% sensitivity and specificity, PLS-DA stands out. The integrity and

security of grape nectars for customers are ensured by this research, which makes a significant contribution to the fight against food fraud [23].

Othman S et.al AI methods have become crucial for quickly and accurately determining quality in the food and agriculture sector when paired with sensing tools. This analysis focuses on recent developments in AI and sensor integration for identifying food tampering and flaws in agricultural products. Complex sensor data is analysed using case-specific AI techniques. The evaluation highlights successful results, with adulteration and defect detection accuracy ranging from 81.2% to 100%. For both researchers and business people, it provides research trends and best practises. With a focus on future advancements, new sensors, and innovative algorithms, challenges and prospects in AI techniques are examined. Real-time monitoring and predictive modelling will be a part of AI-based detection in food and agriculture in the future to ensure product quality and lower the risk of fraud. [24]

Róžańska A et. al This review examines the rapid analysis of volatile chemicals in food using an electronic nose and ultra-fast gas chromatography. Combining it with chemometrics for authentication shows promise. The study provides a system for categorising juices that are "Not From Concentrate" (NFC), such as pure apple and orange juices and blends with defined proportions of base juices. Accurate categorization is possible even with contaminants as low as 1.0% when using supervised statistical approaches, including various chemometric techniques. This approach has a lot of potential for ensuring juice quality and authenticity [25] .

Shankar LS et.al the deliberate tampering with fruits for commercial gain raises major health issues because it might result in chronic illnesses. Due to its covert nature, adulteration persists despite legal restrictions. In order to deal with this, a novel strategy that achieves 94% accuracy using a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), K-means clustering, and Bag of Words approaches is proposed in this research. This study advances public health by presenting a reliable method for identifying tampered fruits and protecting customers.[26]

Naskar H et.al In order to detect adulteration in grape juice, specifically with sugar solution and water, this study proposes a Constant Phase Element (CPE) sensor coated with Poly Methyl Methacrylate (PMMA). Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Box Plot, and Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) are used in the analysis, which uses constant phase data. It is claimed that a Separability Index (SI) may successfully discern between various forms of adulteration. This study helps to increase consumer confidence, ensure the purity of grape juice, and improve food quality control [27].

TABLE I
SUMMARY OF CONVENTIONAL AND MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES AND DATA USED FOR ADULTERATION DETECTION IN FOOD.

Author(s)	Objective	Techniques	Sample
S. P. S. Brighty et al (2021) [28]	Detecting adulteration in fruits using machine learning	Machine learning	Fruits
Huang et al. (2022) [29]	Detecting milk powder adulteration using one-class autoen-coder and infrared spectrum	One-class autoencoder ,Infrared spectrum	Milk powder
Neto et al. (2019) [30]	Detection of milk adulteration	Deep and ensemble learning	Milk
Zhang et al. (2022) [31]	Classifying tea using semi-supervised learning of GAN and E-tongue data	E-tongue data, GAN	Tea
Phillips et al. (2022) [32]	Generating hyperspectral imaging data for honey adulteration detection using variational autoencoders	Variational autoencoders, HSI	Honey
Chakravartula et al. (2022) [33]	Predicting food adulteration using CNN and FT-NIR spectroscopy	CNN, FT-NIR spectroscopy	Coffee
Y.Zhang et al. (2022) [34]	Detecting adulteration in mutton using digital images in the time domain and deep learning	deep learning, Digital images in the time domain	Mutton

IV. CONCLUSION

In this conclusion, given the possible harm that fruit adulteration may cause to consumer health and culinary authenticity, protecting the integrity of fruit products is essential. This study focused on the applicability of several standard and innovative techniques for identifying tampered fruit across a variety of fruit varieties. Though there is potential in the present methodologies, it is important to recognise their limits. The study emphasises how important it is to keep developing strategies to improve the accuracy of fruit adulteration detection. Going forward, the emphasis should be on rectifying these inadequacies, investigating inventive remedies, and adjusting to changing adulteration procedures. Maintaining food safety, consumer trust, and the integrity of the global food supply chain all depend on ongoing advancements in detection technology, which also helps to make the fruit business safer and more open.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The Department of Science and Technology, under the Funds for Infrastructure under Science and Technology (DST- FIST) program, has provided support to the Department of Computer Science and Information Technology at Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad, Maharashtra, India. The grant with sanction no. SR/FST/ETI340/2013 has facilitated the infrastructure and resources required for conducting this research. The authors express their gratitude to the Department and University Authorities for their support in carrying out the study. Additionally, the authors extend their thanks to the Chhatrapati Shahu Maharaj Research Training & Human Development Institute (SARTHI) for their financial assistance in this endeavor.

REFERENCES

- [1] Tewari, S., Agarwal, R. K., Kumar, R. S., & Nakhale, S. (2021) The Pharma Therapeutic Fruits: An Overview, *Journal of Pharmaceutical Research International*, 33(38A): 132 -142.
- [2] Nascimento, G. G., Locatelli, J., Freitas, P. C., & Silva, G. L. (2000). Antibacterial activity of plant extracts and phytochemicals on antibiotic-resistant bacteria. *Brazilian journal of microbiology*, 31,247-256.
- [3] Nanasombat, S., Prasertsin, V., Graisin, K., Shain, H., &Thanaboripat, D. (2002). Efficacy of new enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay for rapid detection of Salmonella in foods. Government Pharmaceutical Organization Report, Bangkok, 51, 53-57.
- [4] Rahman, M. A., Sultan, M. Z., Rahman, M. S., & Rashid, M. A. (2015). Food adulteration: A serious public health concern in Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Pharmaceutical Journal*, 18(1), 1-7.
- [5] Wistaff, E. A., Beller, S., Schmid, A., Neville, J. J., &Nietner, T. (2021). Chemometric analysis of amino acid profiles for detection of fruit juice adulterations–Application to verify authenticity of blood orange juice. *Food Chemistry*, 343, 128452.
- [6] Nagy, S., & Wade, R. L. (1994). Methods to detect adulteration of fruit juice beverages.
- [7] Bhat RV, Waghay K. Street foods in Latin America. *World review of nutrition and dietetics*. 2000 Jan 1;86:123-37.
- [8] Tomar P, Alka G. Food adulteration and its impact on health. *Int J Hom Sci*. 2022;8:164-68.
- [9] Ogrinc NK, Košir IJ, Spangenberg JE, Kidrič J. The application of NMR and MS methods for detection of adulteration of wine, fruit juices, and olive oil. A review. *Analytical and bioanalytical chemistry*. 2003 Jun;376:424-30.
- [10] itaram, Rumila & Divyalaasya, Koti & Ramaraju, Godasritha & Ijmtst, Editor. (2021). Adulteration of Fruits. *International Journal for Modern Trends in Science and Technology*. 7. 52-54. 10.46501/IJMTST0710008.
- [11] Cheng NY, Chen CC, Liang BJ, Tseng SH. Nondestructive evaluation of apple fruit quality by frequency-domain diffuse reflectance spectroscopy: variations in apple skin and flesh. *Applied Sciences*. 2019 Jun 8;9(11):2355.
- [12] Sneha S, Surjith S, Raj SA. A review on food adulteration detection techniques: Methodologies, applications, and challenges. In2023 International Conference on Control, Communication and Computing (ICCC) 2023 May 19 (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- [13] S. P. S. Brightly, G. S. Harini and N. Vishal, "Detection of Adulteration in Fruits Using Machine Learning," 2021 Sixth International Conference on Wireless Communications, Signal Processing and Networking (WiSPNET), Chennai, India, 2021, pp. 37-40, doi: 10.1109/WiSPNET51692.2021.9419402.
- [14] Avula, B.; Katragunta, K.; Osman, A.G.; Ali, Z.; John Adams, S.; Chittiboyina, A.G.; Khan, I.A. Advances in the Chemistry, Analysis and Adulteration of Anthocyanin Rich-Berries and Fruits: 2000–2022. *Molecules* 2023, 28, 560. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules28020560>
- [15] J Fitelsox, Detection of Adulteration in Fruit Juices by Qualitative Determination of Carbohydrates by Gas-Liquid Chromatography, *Journal of Association of Official Analytical Chemists*, Volume 53, Issue 6, 1 November 1970, Pages 1193–1197, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jaoac/53.6.1193>
- [16] Wilbur W. Widmer, Paul F. Cancelon, Steven Nagy, Methods for determining the adulteration of citrus juices, *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, Volume 3,1992,Pages 278-286,ISSN 0924-2244, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-2244\(10\)80012-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-2244(10)80012-3).
- [17] Banti M. Food adulteration and some methods of detection, review. *International Journal of Nutrition and Food Sciences*. 2020;9(3):86-94.
- [18] Sanjitha M, Reddy AS, Joshi A, NP AR, Mahana A. DETECTION OF DISEASE AND ADULTERATION IN FRUITS USING MACHINE LEARNING.
- [19] Calle JL, Ferreira-González M, Ruiz-Rodríguez A, Fernández D, Palma M. Detection of adulterations in fruit juices using machine learning methods over FT-IR spectroscopic data. *Agronomy*. 2022 Mar 11;12(3):683.
- [20] Momtaz M, Bublly SY, Khan MS. Mechanisms and health aspects of food adulteration: A comprehensive review. *Foods*. 2023 Jan 2;12(1):199.
- [21] PH CR, Rakshitha D, Likitha KB, Chetan M. DETECTION OF ADULTERATION IN FRUITS AND VEGETABLES USING MACHINE LEARNING.
- [22] Brightly SP, Harini GS, Vishal N. Detection of adulteration in fruits using machine learning. In2021 Sixth International Conference on Wireless Communications, Signal Processing and Networking (WiSPNET) 2021 Mar 25 (pp. 37-40). IEEE.
- [23] Miaw CS, Sena MM, de Souza SV, Callao MP, Ruisanchez I. Detection of adulterants in grape nectars by attenuated total reflectance Fourier-transform mid-infrared spectroscopy and multivariate classification strategies. *Food chemistry*. 2018 Nov 15;266:254-61.
- [24] Othman S, Mavani NR, Hussain MA, Abd Rahman N, Ali JM. Artificial intelligence-based techniques for adulteration and defect detections in food and agricultural industry: A review. *Journal of Agriculture and Food Research*. 2023 Apr 25:100590.

- [25] Róžańska A, Dymerski T, Namieśnik J. Novel analytical method for detection of orange juice adulteration based on ultra-fast gas chromatography. *Monatshefte für Chemie-Chemical Monthly*. 2018 Sep;149:1615-21.
- [26] Shankar LS, Sravani A, Kumar TS, Rajender S, Basha CZ. Convolution Neural Network (CNN) Based Computerized Classification of Adulterated Fruits with SIFT and Bag of words (BOW). In 2022 4th International Conference on Smart Systems and Inventive Technology (ICSSIT) 2022 Jan 20 (pp. 1068-1073). IEEE.
- [27] Naskar H, Nandeshwar V, Das S. Adulteration detection of grape fruit juice using PCA and LDA pattern recognition technique. In 2018 IEEE Applied Signal Processing Conference (ASPCON) 2018 Dec 7 (pp. 83-86). IEEE.
- [28] S. P. S. Brighty, G. S. Harini, and N. Vishal, "Detection of adulteration in fruits using machine learning," in 2021 Sixth International Conference on Wireless Communications, Signal Processing and Networking (WiSPNET). IEEE, 2021, pp. 37-40.
- [29] G. Huang, L.-m. Yuan, W. Shi, X. Chen, and X. Chen, "Using one-class autoencoder for adulteration detection of milk powder by infrared spectrum," *Food Chemistry*, vol. 372, p. 131219, 2022.
- [30] H. A. Neto, W. L. Tavares, D. C. Ribeiro, R. C. Alves, L. M. Fonseca, and S. V. Campos, "On the utilization of deep and ensemble learning o detect milk adulteration," *BioData mining*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 1-13, 2019.
- [31] S.-F. Zhang, Z. De-Hua, and C. Xiao-Jing, "Analysis of e-tongue data for tea classification based on semi-supervised learning of generative adversarial network," *Chinese Journal of Analytical Chemistry*, vol. 50, no. 2, pp. 77-85, 2022.
- [32] T. Phillips and W. Abdulla, "Variational autoencoders for generating hyperspectral imaging honey adulteration data," in *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2022, pp. 214-221.
- [33] S. S. N. Chakravartula, R. Moscetti, G. Bedini, M. Nardella, and R. Massantini, "Use of convolutional neural network (cnn) combined with ft-nir spectroscopy to predict food adulteration: A case study on coffee," *Food Control*, vol. 135, p. 108816, 2022.
- [34] Y. Zhang, M. Zheng, R. Zhu, and R. Ma, "Detection of adulteration in mutton using digital images in time domain combined with deep learning algorithm," *Meat Science*, vol. 192, p. 108850, 2022.